

**Multidimensional Challenges and Healthcare Access among the Elderly in India:
A Cross-Sectional Study**

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ABSTRACT

Background: India is experiencing a rapid demographic transition with a growing elderly population facing complex social, economic, and health-related challenges. Despite the increasing burden of multimorbidity and disability, limited research explores how multidimensional factors influence healthcare access among older adults. **Objectives:** This study aimed to assess the multifaceted challenges faced by elderly individuals and to examine the associations between these challenges and the affordability of healthcare services in Patna, Bihar. **Methods:** A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted from July to December 2024 among 200 elderly individuals aged ≥ 60 years in urban and semi-urban areas of Patna district. Participants were selected using purposive sampling. Data were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured interview schedule and analysed using SPSS v25. Descriptive statistics summarized key variables, and chi-square tests examined associations between healthcare affordability and selected determinants. **Results:** Among participants, 55% were female and 51% were widowed; 47.5% lived below the poverty line. A large proportion reported inadequate housing (59%), social isolation (72%), and mobility issues (55%). Healthcare services were unaffordable for 64.5% of respondents. Significant associations were found between healthcare affordability and housing adequacy ($p < 0.001$), financial status ($p < 0.001$), mobility ($p < 0.001$), living arrangement ($p < 0.001$), and social support ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Healthcare affordability among the elderly is strongly influenced by multiple interrelated social, economic, and physical factors. Policies aiming to improve elderly healthcare must adopt a multidimensional approach that includes improving living conditions, financial security, social support, and mobility assistance to promote healthy and equitable ageing in India.

Key words: Elderly population, Healthcare access, Multidimensional challenges, Affordability of healthcare, Geriatric health in India.

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Introduction

The global trend of population ageing is driven by several key factors, including declining fertility rates, increased life expectancy, improved survival at older ages, and, to some extent, migration patterns.¹ According to United Nations population projections, the proportion of individuals aged 60 years and above in India is expected to rise from the current 8% to 19% by 2050.² Multimorbidity, defined as the presence of two or more chronic health conditions without prioritizing any as primary, is increasingly common with advancing age. It affects an estimated 20–23% of individuals from 18 years to above 45 years of age, with a higher prevalence among older adults.³ Managing multimorbidity poses significant challenges for healthcare providers, particularly in the elderly population.⁴ Evidence suggests that multimorbidity is associated with negative health outcomes, including increased mortality, disability, and diminished quality of life.⁵ A population-based study conducted in Telangana reported that one in three individuals had at least one non-communicable disease (NCD), and one in five older adults was living with at least one disability.⁶

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines disability as an impairment, activity limitation, or participation restriction arising primarily from health conditions and environmental influences.⁷ There is a well-established association between functional and physical disabilities and the presence of chronic and co-existing illnesses.^{8,9} In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including cardiovascular and musculoskeletal disorders, account for approximately 66.5% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).^{10,11} In 2017, age-related conditions contributed to nearly 51% of both years of life lost (YLL) and years lived with disability (YLD).^{12,13} Despite the rising prevalence of multimorbidity in older adults, much of current medical research and clinical practice remains centered on a single-disease framework, often overlooking the complexity of multiple concurrent conditions. However, as research on multimorbidity and its relationship with disability has progressed, findings consistently show that the risk and severity of disability increase proportionally with the number of chronic conditions an individual has.^{14,15}

In India, ageing presents complex, interwoven challenges that significantly compromise healthcare access for the elderly. Economically, high out-of-pocket (OOP) costs amounting to approximately 83% of all health expenditures often push older adults into catastrophic health spending, with limited insurance coverage failing to protect against outpatient and medication expenses. A study conducted in Punjab showed non-communicable diseases frequently experience catastrophic OOP costs for treatment and diagnostics despite having insurance, with lower-income families bearing the brunt.^{16,17} Geographically, longer travel distances present another barrier: older adults typically travel 14 km for outpatient and 44 km for inpatient care, with rural elders disproportionately affected, leading to reduced service utilization. Mobility challenges and inadequate transportation options thus exacerbate delays in seeking care.¹⁸

Socially, many Indians face isolation and lack of caregiver support; in rural areas only about 50% of elderly are accompanied by family to medical visits, and those living alone particularly women encounter disproportionately greater access issues. Inadequate housing and environmental constraints such as homes not adapted to ageing or extreme weather further complicate navigation to healthcare services and increase health vulnerabilities.¹⁹ Without addressing these socioeconomic, geographic, infrastructural, and social determinants, efforts to improve healthcare access risk remaining insufficient, particularly for India's rapidly growing and increasingly vulnerable elderly population.

Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively assess the multidimensional challenges spanning social, economic, physical, and environmental domains faced by the elderly population in India, and to explore how these factors influence their access to healthcare services. By identifying the key determinants associated with healthcare affordability and utilization among older adults, the study seeks to generate evidence that can inform geriatric health policy, guide the design of age-friendly healthcare systems, and support the development of integrated interventions to promote healthy and dignified ageing.

Methodology

The study was conducted over a six-month period from July to December 2024. It was a community-based cross-sectional study carried out in the Patna district of Bihar, India, encompassing a mix of urban and semi-urban areas, including Patna city, Kankarbagh, Ashiyana-Digha, Danapur block, and the SAHARA Old Age Home managed by HelpAge India. Patna was purposively selected as the study location due to its rapidly growing elderly population and the wide range of socio-economic backgrounds represented in the district. This context offered a suitable setting to explore the multidimensional challenges faced by older adults and to examine how various factors particularly living arrangements, financial status, and functional health impact their access to healthcare services.

Sample Size Calculation: The sample size was calculated based on an estimated 64.8% prevalence of chronic ailments among the elderly⁷, as reported in national-level geriatric health surveys. Using the standard formula for cross-sectional studies:

$$n = \frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p)}{d^2}$$

To account for clustering within the study settings (including neighbourhoods and institutional home), a design effect of 2 was applied, yielding an adjusted sample size of 176. After accounting for a 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was $176 \times 2 = 352$.

Sampling Method: Participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure the inclusion of elderly individuals from diverse living arrangements, including those residing in institutional settings (such as old age homes), those living independently, and those residing with family members. Out of the total 200 participants, 98 elderly individuals (49.0%) were from institutional settings, ensuring adequate representation of this subgroup. The inclusion of institutionalized elders was intentional to capture their specific challenges and to allow for direct comparison with community-dwelling elders. This one-to-one comparative approach provided deeper insights into how living arrangements influence health status, social support, and access to healthcare services. Individuals aged 60 years and above, who were permanent residents of the study area, willing to participate, and able to provide informed consent were included in the study. Individuals with severe cognitive impairment that prevented them from comprehending the interview process were excluded.

Data Collection Tools and Procedures: Data were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured interview schedule administered through face-to-face interviews by trained field investigators fluent in the local language (Hindi). The tool was developed based on a review of validated instruments used in geriatric health studies and was pilot-tested for clarity and contextual relevance among a small sample. The interview schedule captured detailed information across several domains, including socio-demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, marital status, education, and income), living arrangements and housing conditions, social support systems, mental and physical health status, mobility limitations, presence of chronic illnesses or disabilities, and access, affordability, and utilization of healthcare services. Mental health status was assessed through self-reported symptoms such as persistent sadness, anxiety, and sleep disturbances. In addition, participants were asked whether they had sought any treatment, counselling, or psychological help in the past six months. No standardized screening tools were used for diagnosing mental health conditions.

Statistical analysis: All data were entered and cleaned using Microsoft Excel and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) trial version 25. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, including the chi-square test, were applied to examine associations between healthcare affordability and selected independent variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Thematic clusters show overlapping challenges impacting well-being. Poor housing, overcrowding, and unsafe conditions are common. Many face isolation with little social support, contributing to mental health issues like anxiety and depression. Financial hardship limits access to healthcare, worsened by transportation difficulties. Physical health problems, such as chronic illness and limited mobility, further affect daily life. Environmental risks, including homes not suited to extreme weather and unsafe neighbourhoods, increase vulnerability. Together, these factors reveal the complex barriers faced by people in underserved communities.

Socio-Demographic and Health Profile of the Elderly Study Participants: The study included 200 elderly individuals aged 60 years and above. The largest proportion of participants (44.9%) belonged to the 60–69 years age group, followed by 35.5% in the 70–79 years category and 19.5% aged 80 years or older. Females constituted a slightly higher proportion (55%) compared to males (45%).

A majority of the respondents were widowed (51.0%), while 41.5% were currently married and 7.5% were either divorced or separated. Regarding living arrangements, nearly half (49.0%) resided in institutional care settings, while 34.0% lived with their families, and 17.0% lived alone.

In terms of educational attainment, 38.5% of participants were illiterate, 42.5% had completed primary education, and only 19.0% had attained higher education. Socio-economically, 47.5% were classified as living below the poverty line, while 38.5% were from middle-income households and 14.0% belonged to affluent backgrounds. Occupationally, more than half of the

respondents (57.5%) were retired, 22.0% were currently employed, and 20.5% were unemployed. Health-wise, 53.5% reported having a chronic illness, 25.0% were differently abled, and 21.5% had a history of mental illness. (Table 1).

The religious composition was predominantly Hindu (80.0%), followed by Muslims (13.5%) and other religions (6.5%). In terms of social engagement, 64.5% of the elderly were socially isolated, whereas 35.5% were active in community groups. The study reveals key vulnerabilities among the elderly that require focused intervention. Most participants were aged 60–69, offering a chance for early care. High numbers of women and widows point to social and financial insecurity, worsened by weak support systems. Nearly half lived in institutions, raising concerns about care quality. Low education and high illiteracy limit health literacy and disease management. Many were economically dependent, with almost half below the poverty line. Chronic illness, disability, and mental health issues, along with isolation, call for integrated, community-based care. Health systems must improve primary care, oversight, and support tailored to social and cultural needs (Table 1).

Table- 1: Socio-Demographic and Health Profile of the Elderly Study participants (N = 200).

Indicator		No.	%
Age Distribution	60–69 years	90	44.9
	70–79 years	71	35.5
	80+ years	39	19.5
Gender	Male	90	45.0
	Female	110	55.0
Marital Status	Married	83	41.5
	Widowed	102	51.0
	Divorced/Separated	15	7.5
Living Arrangement	With family	68	34.0
	Alone	34	17.0
	Institutional care	98	49.0
Educational Attainment	Illiterate	77	38.5
	Primary Education	85	42.5
	Higher Education	38	19.0
Economic Status	Below Poverty Line	95	47.5
	Middle Income	77	38.5
	Affluent	28	14.0
Employment Status	Retired	115	57.5
	Currently employed	44	22.0
	Unemployed	41	20.5
Health Status	Mental Illness	43	21.5
	Chronic illness	107	53.5
	Differently abled	50	25.0
Religion	Hindu	160	80.0
	Muslim	27	13.5
	Other	13	6.5
Social Engagement	Active in community groups	71	35.5
	Socially isolated	129	64.5

Assessment of Multidimensional Challenges Faced by Elderly Participants: Table 2 presents a comprehensive overview of the various challenges faced by senior citizens in the study. Nearly half of the elderly participants (49.5%) were residing in institutional care, while 29.0% lived with their families and 21.5% lived alone. Despite these living arrangements, 59.0% reported inadequate home infrastructure, and 47.0% were living in unsafe or substandard housing. Additionally, 58.5% experienced crowded or inadequate space, limiting their mobility within the household.(Table 2)

Social challenges were also prevalent. A significant proportion of participants (72.0%) reported feeling socially isolated, and 56.5% had limited social support networks. Mental health concerns were common, with 71.5% of elderly individuals experiencing symptoms of depression or anxiety, highlighting a critical area of concern in geriatric well-being. In terms of healthcare access, although 74.0% had access to public healthcare services, 60.0% of the respondents reported difficulty reaching healthcare facilities due to transportation barriers. Affordability was a major issue, with 64.5% indicating that healthcare services were not financially accessible to them.

Economic instability was reflected in the finding that 40.5% of participants lived below the poverty line and more than half (53.5%) struggled to afford housing and basic utilities. Only a small fraction (13.5%) reported being economically affluent. Physical well-being was also compromised, with 55.0% of respondents experiencing mobility issues and 76.0% suffering from chronic illnesses or disabilities. These health problems likely contribute to increased dependency and reduced quality of life.

Environmental concerns were noted, as 60.0% of the participants reported that their homes were not adapted to extreme weather conditions, and 58.0% lived in neighbourhoods perceived as unsafe (Table 2).

Table-2: Assessment of Multidimensional Challenges Faced by Elderly Participants (N = 200)

	Category	Key Areas of Concern	N = 200	%
Housing Conditions	Living Arrangements	Living alone	43	21.5
		Living with family	58	29.0
		Institutional care	99	49.5
	Home Infrastructure	Accessible homes	82	41.0
		Inadequate infrastructure	118	59.0
	Safety Concerns	Safe and Adequate Housing	106	53.0
		Unsafe or Inadequate Housing	94	47.0
	Adequacy of Space	Adequate space for mobility	83	41.5
Crowded or inadequate space		117	58.5	
Social Issues	Social Isolation	Feel socially isolated	144	72.0
		Regular social interaction	66	33.0
	Social Support Networks	Strong social support	87	43.5
		Limited social support	113	56.5
	Mental Health Concerns	Experience depression or anxiety	143	71.5
No significant mental health concerns		57	28.5	
Healthcare Access	Access to Healthcare Services	Access to public healthcare	148	74.0
		Access to private healthcare	52	26.0
	Transportation to Healthcare Services	Able to reach healthcare services	80	40.0
		Difficulty accessing healthcare services	120	60.0
	Affordability of Healthcare	Healthcare services are affordable	71	35.5
Healthcare services are not affordable		129	64.5	
Economic Concerns	Financial Stability	Below poverty line	81	40.5
		Middle income	92	46.0
		Affluent	27	13.5
	Housing Affordability	Affordable housing	93	46.5
		Struggling to afford housing and utilities	107	53.5
Physical Well-being	Mobility Issues	Experience mobility challenges	110	55.0
		No significant mobility issues	90	45.0
	Chronic Illnesses/Disabilities	Suffer from chronic illnesses	152	76.0
		No chronic illnesses or disabilities	48	24.0
Environmental Factors	Climate and Weather Conditions	Housing adapted for extreme weather	80	40.0
		Housing not adapted for extreme weather	120	60.0
	Neighbourhood Conditions	Safe neighbourhood	84	42.0
		Unsafe neighbourhood	116	58.0

Association between Affordability of Healthcare and different Challenges

Table 3 highlights the statistically significant associations between healthcare affordability and multiple challenges faced by the elderly. A significantly higher proportion of those living in safe and adequate housing reported healthcare as affordable (77.5%) compared to those in unsafe or inadequate housing (22.5%), with the association being statistically significant ($\chi^2=22.6$, $p<0.001$).

Financial status showed a strong association with healthcare affordability. Among those who found healthcare affordable, the majority belonged to the middle-income (53.5%) or affluent (38.0%) groups, whereas 58.1% of those who found healthcare unaffordable were below the poverty line ($\chi^2=68.3$, $p<0.001$). Notably, no respondents from the affluent category reported healthcare to be unaffordable (Table 3).

Table-3: Association between Affordability of Healthcare and different Challenges faced by the Senior Citizens

Variable	Category	Affordable (n=71)		Not Affordable (n=129)		Chi-square (p-value)
		No.	%	No.	%	
Housing Conditions	Safe and Adequate Housing	55	77.5	51	39.5	$\chi^2=26.45$ (p<0.001)
	Unsafe or Inadequate Housing	16	22.5	78	60.5	
Financial Instability	Below Poverty Line	6	8.5	75	58.1	$\chi^2=68.3$ (p<0.001)
	Middle Income	38	53.5	54	41.9	
	Affluent	27	38.0	0	0.0	
Mobility Issues	Yes	18	25.4	92	71.3	$\chi^2= 39.09$ (p<0.001)
	No	53	74.6	37	28.7	
Living Arrangement	Living Alone	5	7.0	38	29.5	$\chi^2=64.39$ (p<0.001)
	Living with Family	45	63.4	13	10.1	
	Institutional Care	21	29.6	78	60.5	
Social Support	Strong Social Support	56	78.9	31	24.0	$\chi^2=56.04$ (p<0.001)
	Limited Social Support	15	21.1	98	76.0	

Mobility issues were also significantly linked with affordability; 74.6% of elderly individuals without mobility issues could afford healthcare, whereas 71.3% of those with mobility challenges found it unaffordable ($\chi^2=40.9$, p<0.001). Living arrangement demonstrated a strong correlation with affordability. Those living with family had the highest proportion of healthcare affordability (63.4%), while those in institutional care (60.5%) or living alone (29.5%) were more likely to report healthcare as unaffordable ($\chi^2=41.7$, p<0.001). Social support was another critical determinant. Elderly individuals with strong social support were significantly more likely to afford healthcare (78.9%) compared to those with limited support (21.1%). Conversely, 76.0% of those with limited social support reported healthcare as unaffordable ($\chi^2=53.2$, p<0.001). (Table 3)

The analysis shows healthcare affordability is closely linked to poor housing, limited mobility, and social isolation among the elderly. Supportive social networks improve access, while affluent individuals report fewer issues, highlighting deep inequities. Addressing affordability requires integrated reforms that connect healthcare with housing, income support, and community-based care.

Discussion

The present study highlights key socio-demographic vulnerabilities among the elderly population, including a higher proportion of females, widowhood, low educational attainment, and economic dependency. These findings are consistent with national and regional data, such as the National Sample Survey (NSS), which reports high levels of illiteracy and financial insecurity among older adults, particularly women.^{20,21} Nearly half of the participants resided in institutional care, which is higher than national estimates, possibly reflecting specific sampling characteristics.²² A significant proportion (53.5%) reported chronic illnesses, while 25% were differently abled, and 21.5% had mental health concerns. These findings align with studies linking multimorbidity with disability and poor quality of life among the elderly.^{23,24} Mental health status in this study was based on self-reported symptoms such as persistent sadness, anxiety, and sleep disturbances, as well as participants' responses regarding whether they had sought treatment or counselling in the past six months. However, it is important to note that no standardized diagnostic tools were used to assess mental health conditions, which may have led to underreporting or misclassification.

Additionally, the study revealed substantial social challenges, with 64.5% of participants experiencing social isolation and only 35.5% actively engaged in community life. Similar trends have been reported in Indian settings, where lack of caregiver support and declining social networks are common, especially in rural and urban poor regions.^{25,26} These multidimensional challenges economic, physical, social, and mental are closely intertwined and likely influence access to and utilization of healthcare services.^{27,28}

The present study found that nearly half of the elderly participants (49.5%) were residing in institutional care, a figure notably higher than national estimates. This may reflect unique contextual factors in the study area, such as weakened family support systems and limited availability of informal care giving, particularly in urban and economically strained settings of

Patna.^{22,29} Additionally, a large proportion of participants reported challenges related to housing 59.0% reported inadequate infrastructure, 47.0% lived in unsafe conditions, and 58.5% experienced limited living space. These findings highlight a significant lack of age-appropriate housing within the study population and reinforce the need for housing policies that prioritize the needs of older adults, consistent with WHO's emphasis on age-friendly environments.²⁸

Social and emotional challenges were equally prominent, consistent with previous research highlighting isolation among elderly widows, those living alone, or institutionalized individuals.^{25,26} Mental health concerns such as depression and anxiety were reported by 71.5%, a figure significantly higher than national averages, indicating an urgent need for routine geriatric mental health screening.^{24,28} Access to healthcare remained constrained, with 60.0% of participants reporting transportation barriers and 64.5% stating that healthcare was unaffordable. These patterns are supported by findings from Misra et al., who documented significant associations between distance, transport, and healthcare utilization among older adults.²⁷

Economic vulnerability was also a major concern, with 40.5% living below the poverty line and 53.5% struggling to afford basic needs, reflects existing evidence showing inadequate pension coverage and high financial dependency among the elderly in India.^{20,21} Physically, more than half reported mobility challenges and a large majority lived with chronic illnesses or disabilities, reinforcing previous findings that functional limitations increase with age and multimorbidity.^{23,24} Environmental inadequacies further compounded these challenges; 60.0% lived in homes not adapted to extreme weather, and 58.0% perceived their neighbourhood as unsafe. These findings highlight the urgent need to address environmental, infrastructural, and social determinants through integrated policies and community-based elder care programs.^{28,29}

The present study identified strong and statistically significant associations between healthcare affordability and key determinants such as housing quality, economic status, and social support. Elderly individuals living in safe and adequate housing were more likely to report healthcare as affordable, suggesting that housing conditions in the study population directly influenced financial accessibility to care. This finding highlights the compounded disadvantage faced by those in poor living environments.^{28,30} Additionally, none of the affluent participants in our sample reported healthcare as unaffordable, whereas a majority of those living below the poverty line did under scoring the stark economic divide in access to care. These findings are consistent with national data indicating high out-of-pocket expenditures and limited financial protection for elderly individuals, especially those from low-income backgrounds.^{20,21,29}

Mobility limitations were another important predictor, with elderly individuals experiencing mobility challenges being significantly less likely to afford healthcare. This aligns with findings that physical disability can restrict healthcare access due to increased dependency, higher transport costs, and caregiver needs.^{23,24} Living arrangement was also significantly correlated with affordability; elderly individuals living with family reported better healthcare affordability than those in institutional care or living alone. This reflects the supportive role families continue to play in financing and facilitating access to care for the elderly in India.²⁶

Social support emerged as one of the strongest determinants of healthcare affordability. Individuals with strong support networks were far more likely to find healthcare affordable, whereas those with limited support reported unaffordability in nearly three-quarters of cases. This is consistent with studies showing that social networks help mitigate both emotional and financial burdens associated with old-age illnesses.^{25,27}

Conclusion

The present study highlights the complex interaction of social, economic, physical, and environmental factors influencing healthcare access among the elderly in India. Financial insecurity, inadequate housing, social isolation, chronic illnesses, and limited mobility were significantly associated with healthcare affordability. The findings emphasize that access to care is not solely about service availability but is closely tied to broader determinants such as poverty, social support, and living conditions. A multidimensional approach to elderly care is essential one that addresses not just health services but also the underlying social and economic challenges. Policy measures such as expanding mobile health services, enhancing pension coverage, promoting age-friendly housing, and strengthening community-based support can substantially improve healthcare access and overall well-being among India's ageing population.

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